

Effects of Sharp Practices on Rural Dwellers' Cultural Integrity in Oyo State

Adelakun, S. A., Ayoade, A. R., Adebayo, O. O., Adewole, W. A.

Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development, Ladoké Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Sharp practices especially in the rural areas had been bedeviling agricultural development at an alarming magnitude. The study therefore examined the effects of sharp practices on rural dwellers' cultural integrity in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study specifically described various sharp practices related to cultural integrity and cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers. The study employed multistage sampling technique to select 101 rural dwellers from Oyo States. The data for the study were obtained through the use of semi structured interview schedule. The data were analyzed with descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the null hypothesis.

*Financial inducement for leadership position (WMS = 2.80) was the most common sharp practices in political terrain of the rural settings as examination malpractices (WMS = 2.63) was most common in the educational sector while appreciation and reward for wealthy individuals irrespective of their dubious origins and unscrupulous circumstances underlining their riches as well as favouritism (WMS = 2.48) were the major occurrences in religious circle. Political sharp practices ($r = 0.282^{***}$, 0.004), educational sharp practices ($r = 0.241^{**}$, 0.015) and religion sharp practices ($r = 0.280^{**}$, 0.004) were significant and positively related to rural dwellers' cultural integrity status. Conclusively, it was recorded that ripening of fruits using chemical products with a WMS of 2.82 was the most common sharp practice which falls under the economic institution of the society while keeping of virginity, frowning against homosexuality and bestiality respectively were the topmost cultural integrity item under moral commitment among the rural dwellers. Propensity of safeguarding cultural integrity status increases with a unit decrease in the level of sharp practices especially in the economic, political, family and educational institutions of the rural communities. Therefore, rural dwellers should desist from unscrupulous practices such as using chemicals for fruit ripening and also, encourages keeping of virginity among younger ones as a way of sustaining cultural integrity.*

.Keywords: *Child training, Cultural integrity, Marital infidelity, Sharp practices*

1. INTRODUCTION

Culture is a sociological concept that encapsulates norms, rules of behaviour, customs, values, beliefs, practices and collective identities shared in common by people. Bamikole (2008) opines that it also underlies the contents of human associations and social movements. Traditional cultural practice reflects values and beliefs held by members of a community, households or social groupings for periods often spanning generations.

Integrity “refers to the consistent alignment of, and adherence to, shared values, principles and norms for upholding and prioritising the public interest in the public sector (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2017). OECD (2017) also noted that integrity as a concept has two distinctive stems, namely; personal and moral integrity which consequently beget cultural integrity.

Cultural integrity is a practice of upholding the norms, rules of behaviour, customs, beliefs, practices and collective identities of the society, and most of its significant attributes include honesty, discipline, uprightness, keeping of virginity and morality. For instance, the sanctity of high moral values made it possible for agricultural products such as banana, plantain, oranges and yam tubers to be displayed at strategic location unmanned; with the placement of the equivalent cowries representing the worth by the farmer and passersby come and pick their choice and pay (Ladele and Fadairo, 2013). Similarly, respect for elders had also been identified as a means of showcasing proper home training which is the channel to diagnose the potential attributes of the parents of the children in question. The respect for elder could be in form of greeting, helping them with their luggage as well as yielding to correction and advice from elders.

Sharp practices according to Business Dictionary (2013) are acts of cunningness, deceit, misinterpretation, trickery and other unscrupulous behaviours just short of legal procedures. Other forms of sharp practices include gossiping, favouritisms, marital infidelity, adulteration of produce or inputs, collusion or conspiracy and negligence of duty. Many individuals in the rural areas have perfected several ways of cutting corners: including manipulating or circumventing or avoiding legal modes of conduct, for several reasons (Ladele and Agboola, 2015).

Despite the damaging effects of sharp practices in the society, limited or no research on its effects on cultural integrity and methods of preventing them in the developing countries especially in the rural areas have been carried out so far. One of the reasons is that the importance of preventive methods for sustainable development of rural areas might have been underestimated. Another reason is the relatively high costs of running a survey – this is even more so if the surveys take place in remote rural areas. Finally, getting data on causes, methods for preventing sharp practices and the preventive measures are very sensitive issues people might be hesitant to report (Ladele and Fadairo, 2013). Underreporting or refusing to answer might be serious problems when running a representative survey in the field. Against this background, this research work tends to examine effects of sharp practices on rural dwellers’ cultural integrity in Oyo - State, Nigeria.

Objectives:

- i. describe the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents in the study area;

- ii. identify various sharp practices related to cultural integrity in the study area;
- iii. determine the cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers' in the study area.

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant relationship between various sharp practices in the study area and rural dwellers' cultural integrity status

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Oyo State. It lies between latitude 70°N and 190N of the equator and between 2.5°E and 5°E of the prime meridian. The State has a total population of 5.6 million going by the provisional population figure of 2006 (Census, 2006), and a land area of 27,140,000 square kilometer. Annual mean rainfall ranges above 1000mm; rainy season in the state averages eight months in a year. Rains start in Oyo State during the first week of March with storms. Mean temperature varies from daily minimum of 18.9°C to a daily maximum of 35°C . Humidity is quite high in Oyo State. Relative humidity in the State is 70 percent with a maximum of about 60 percent in the evening and a maximum of around 80 percent in the morning. The settlement pattern shows that so many people of different Nigerian ethnic background reside in Oyo State. The Yoruba ethnic group constitutes the majority of the population living in Oyo State. There are also non-Nigerians who live in Oyo State. The ten Local Government Areas (LGAs) are Akinyele, Ido, Olorunsogo, Ona-Ara, and Oriire. Others include Oyo West, Surulere, Ibarapa North, Iwajowa and Egbeda.

Population of this study involved all the rural dwellers in Oyo State, Nigeria. This includes all men and women in the rural communities in Oyo Nigeria. The study employed multistage sampling technique in selecting sample for this study. This study drew its sample from 2018 NDHS (Nigeria Demographic and Health Surveys) which is a national sample survey that provides up-to-date information on demographic and health indicators. The 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2018 NDHS) is the sixth survey of its kind to be implemented by the National Population Commission. Then, the sample was selected using a stratified, two-stage cluster design, with enumeration areas (EAs) as the sampling units for the first stage. The second stage involved a complete listing of households carried out in each of the 1,400 selected EAs from each state. The third stage involved random selection of 3% of the households (14,000) which implies that a total of 101 rural dwellers were considered out of 226 rural dwellers from the selected cells in Oyo state.

Table 1: Sampling frame for the study

States	ADPs ZONES (50%)	Purposive selection of 2 Blocks	Random selection of 2 cells per block	Number of registered rural dwellers with NDHS	Number of selected rural dwellers (45%)
Oyo state	Ogbomoso	Ogo oluwa	Ibapon	27	12
			Owolaake	35	16
		Oriire	Atere	21	9
			Saamo	29	13
	Oyo	Afijio	Jobele	22	10
			Iware	27	12
	Atiba	Offa meta	35	15	
		Akinmorin	30	14	
Sub-total	2	4	8	226	101

Source: Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS, 2018)

Primary data was collected by the use of semi structured interview schedule. The interview schedule contained both open and close ended questions which aided the collection of relevant information on the objectives of this research work. A mixed method design was adopted for this study using a qualitative and quantitative approaches. The quantitative method was carried out through correlational and descriptive research design while the qualitative method was carried out using personal observation and a well-structured interview guide, and Focus Group Discussion was organized for rural dwellers.

The statistic analytical tools that was used for this study include both descriptive and inferential statistical tool [Pearson’s Products Moment Correlation (PPMC)] was used for the formulated hypothesis of the study.

3. DISCUSSION

Distribution of respondents by socioeconomic characteristics

Age (years)

The result in figure 4.1 indicates that 35.6 percent of the respondents were between age range 41-50 years, 32.8 percent of the respondents were between 51-60 years, 8.9 percent were above 60 years, while 5.9 percent of the respondents were ≤ 30 years. This implies that majority of the respondents are still young, they were still in the right age to understand how the menace of sharp practices has permeated the fabrics of our society and has drastically affected our cultural integrity.

Sex

It was revealed that 60.4 percent of the respondents were male while 39.6 percent of the respondents were female. The finding therefore indicates that most of the respondents were male.

Marital status

It was revealed that majority of the 66.3 percent of the respondents were married, 14.9 percent of the respondents were divorced, 8.9 percent of the respondents were single, 6.9 percent of the respondents were widowed while another 2.9 percent of the respondents were separated. Based on the findings, it was observed that married people are expected to be the custodian of our culture and are also supposed to transfer the cultural values and norms to their children. Therefore, having majority of the respondents as married would aid the transfer of the cultural integrity from one generation to the other.

Religion

It was revealed that 69.3 percent of the respondents practices Christianity, 17.8 percent of the respondents were practicing traditional religion while while 12.9 were practicing Islam. majority of respondents from Oyo State (69.3%), Ogun State (67.9%) and Ondo State (63.8%) dominantly practiced Christianity religion, though some still engaged in other religious practices. The result therefore implies that several religions in Nigeria co-exist in the study area though majority sampled of the rural dwellers are Christians. This is an indication that different religious groups co-exist in the study area and there is no religious barrier in the level of involvement in desired livelihood activities.

Educational level

This revealed that 36.6 percent of the respondents has secondary school education, 34.7 percent had primary school education, 9.9 percent had tertiary institution education. However, 18.8 percent of the respondents had no formal education. It was observed that majority of the respondents had formal education which implies that most of the farmers are end enlightened.

Household size

It was revealed that 53.5 percent of the respondents had household size between 5-8 members, 29.7 percent had household size between 9 and above members, while 16.8 percent had household size between 1-4 members. Mean household size was 9 members. The household size was presumably large which could be associated with the need to make family labour available for farming operations in the rural areas. This implies that most rural dwellers and households ventured into maintaining large household size probably to ensure adequate supply of family labour for agricultural production.

Primary occupation

This results shows that 48.5 percent of the respondents engaged in farming as their primary occupation, 31.7 percent engaged in trading as their primary occupation, 9.9 percent engaged in civil services and artisan activities respectively. This therefore implies that majority of the respondents predominantly betrothed in farming as their primary livelihood.

Secondary occupation

This result revealed that 53.5 percent of the respondents engaged in trading as their secondary occupation, 25.7 percent engaged in artisan activities as their secondary occupation, 19.8 percent engaged in civil services as their secondary occupation while 1.0 percent engages in farming as

their secondary occupation. The result therefore shows that majority of the respondents engaged in trading as their secondary occupation.

Year residency

It was revealed that 50.5 percent of the respondents had spent between 11-20 years in their areas, 30.7 percent had spent 21-30 years in their areas, 10.9 percent had spent 31-40 years in their areas, 4.9 percent had spent 41-50 years in their areas, 3.0 percent had spent 1-10 years in their areas while (0.0) percent of the respondents spent above 50 years in their areas. 2.1 percent of the respondents had spent 41-50 years in their areas while (0.0) percent of the respondents had spent above 50 years in the study areas. Moreover, the mean years of residency was 22.11 years which is an indication that they had spent certain number of years in the study areas and this should help them in understanding the latest development and cultural values in the areas.

Membership of social organization

It was revealed that 96.0 percent of the respondents from Oyo State reported that they were members of social organization while only 4.0 percent were non-member of social organizations.

Source of capital

It was revealed that 39.6 percent of the respondents obtained their capital through personal savings, 24.8 percent of the respondents obtained their capital through cooperative associations, 13.9 percent of the respondents obtained their capital through thrift and contributions, 8.9 percent of the respondents obtained their own capital from commercial banks, 6.9 percent obtained their capital from private money lenders while 5.9 percent obtained their capital from relatives/friends. The finding therefore revealed that most of the respondents relied on their personal savings to carry out their livelihood activities, an indication that availability of funds for farming is highly dependent on personal savings

Table2: Distribution of respondents by socioeconomic characteristics

Socio-economic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
≤30	6	5.9
31-40	17	16.8
41-50	36	35.6
51-60	33	32.8
Above 60	9	8.9
Mean (x) = 47.44 years;		
Sex		
Male	61	60.4
Female	40	39.6
Marital status		

Single	9	8.9
Married	67	66.3
Divorced	15	14.9
Widowed	7	6.9
Separated	3	2.9
Religion		
Islam	13	12.9
Christianity	70	69.3
Traditional Religion	18	17.8
Educational level		
No formal education	19	18.8
Primary school education	35	34.7
Secondary school education	37	36.6
Tertiary school education	10	9.9
Years spent in school (years)		
0	19	18.8
1-6	35	34.7
7-12	37	36.6
13-16	10	9.9
Above 16	0	0.0
Mean (x) = 8.06 years		
Household size		
1-2	0	0.0
3-4	17	16.8
5-6	22	21.8
7-8	32	31.7
9-10	22	21.8
Above 10	8	7.9
Mean (x) = 7.41 years		
Primary occupation		
Farming	49	48.5
Trading	32	31.7
Civil services	10	9.9
Artisan activities	10	9.9
Secondary occupation		
Farming	1	1.0
Trading	54	53.5
Civil services	20	19.8
Artisan activities	26	25.7
Years of residency		
1-10	3	3.0
11-20	51	50.5
21-30	31	30.7

31-40	11	10.9
41-50	5	4.9
Above 50	0	0.0
Mean (x) = 22.11 years		
Membership of social organization		
Members	97	96.0
Non-Members	4	4.0
Source of capital		
Personal savings	40	39.6
Cooperative Association	25	24.8
Private money lenders	7	6.9
Relatives/friends	6	5.9
Commercial Bank	9	8.9
Thrift and contribution	14	13.9

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Distribution of respondents by various sharp practices

Under Political institution, the various sharp practices include financial inducement for leadership position with a WMS of 2.80 which was ranked 1st, kidnapping/banditry with a WMS of 2.63 was ranked 2nd, manipulation of election results with a WMS of 2.48 was ranked 3rd.

Under Educational institution, various sharp practices include examination malpractices with a WMS of 2.63 which was ranked 1st, the use of fake certificates with a WMS of 2.33 was ranked 2nd, negligence of duty with a WMS of 2.23 was ranked 3rd. In Religious institution, various sharp practices include appreciation and reward for wealthy individuals irrespective of their dubious origins and unscrupulous circumstances underlining their riches with a WMS of 2.48 which was ranked 1st, favouritism with a WMS of 2.48 was ranked 2nd, collusion or conspiracy with a WMS of 2.47 was ranked 3rd. Economically, various sharp practices in the rank order include, ripening of fruit using chemical products with a WMS of 2.82 was ranked 1st, request for gratitude money or request for gifts for usual services with a WMS of 2.58 was ranked 2nd, embezzlement of funds with a WMS of 2.57 was ranked 3rd.

Family, various sharp practices include marital infidelity with a WMS of 2.64 which was ranked 1st, child labour with a WMS of 2.55 was ranked 2nd, unfaithfulness with a WMS of 2.51 was ranked 3rd.

In other words, for respondents from Oyo State, financial inducement for leadership position with a WMS of 2.80 was the most common sharp practices in political terrain of the rural settings as examination malpractices with a WMS of 2.63 was most common in the educational sector while appreciation and reward for wealthy individuals irrespective of their dubious origins and unscrupulous circumstances underlining their riches as well as favouritism with a WMS of 2.48

were the major occurrences in religious circle. Moreover, ripening of fruit using chemical products with a WMS of 2.82 was the prominent sharp practices perpetrated in the economic sector of the society while marital infidelity with a WMS of 2.64 was most common sharp practices in the family sector, among members of the society.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by various sharp practices (Oyo State)

Various sharp practices	Very Often	Often	Rarely	Not all	WMS	Rank
Political institution						
Financial inducement for leadership position	81(80.2)	20(19.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2.80	1 st
Manipulation of election results	54(53.5)	41(40.6)	6(5.9)	0(0.0)	2.48	3 rd
Impersonation of Permanent Voters' Cards	42(41.6)	46(45.5)	13(12.9)	0(0.0)	2.29	5 th
Perversion of justice through connection	43(42.6)	40(39.6)	17(16.8)	1(1.0)	2.24	6 th
Snatching of vital electoral materials	57(56.4)	29(28.7)	15(14.9)	0(0.0)	2.42	4 th
Kidnapping/banditry	69(68.3)	27(26.7)	5(5.0)	0(0.0)	2.63	2 nd
Educational institution						
Examination malpractices	68(67.3)	29(28.7)	4(4.0)	0(0.0)	2.63	1 st
Using of fake certificates	48(47.5)	39(38.6)	13(12.9)	1(1.0)	2.33	2 nd
Negligence of duty	43(42.6)	38(37.6)	20(19.8)	0(0.0)	2.23	3 rd
Religious institution						
Matchmaking arrangement in religious institutions	46(45.5)	42(41.6)	13(12.9)	0(0.0)	2.33	4 th
Collusion or conspiracy	56(55.4)	37(36.6)	7(6.9)	1(1.0)	2.47	3 rd
Appreciation and reward for wealthy individuals irrespective of their dubious origins and unscrupulous circumstances underlining their riches	56(55.4)	37(36.6)	8(7.9)	0(0.0)	2.48	1 st
Favouritism	60(59.4)	29(28.7)	12(11.9)	0(0.0)	2.48	1 st
Fake prophecies from religious leaders	43(42.6)	42(42.6)	15(14.9)	1(1.0)	2.26	5 th
Economic institution						
Ripening of fruit using chemical products	83(82.2)	18(17.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2.82	1 st
Embezzlement of funds	61(60.4)	37(36.6)	3(3.0)	0(0.0)	2.57	3 rd
Request for gratitude money or request for gifts for usual services	61(60.4)	38(37.6)	2(2.0)	0(0.0)	2.58	2 nd
Diversion of funds	60(59.4)	39(38.6)	2(2.0)	0(0.0)	2.57	3 rd

Adulteration of produce and inputs	48(47.5)	42(41.6)	10(9.9)	1(1.0)	2.36	8 th
Modification/manipulation of measurement	55(54.6)	33(32.7)	13(12.9)	0(0.0)	2.42	7 th
Pilfering (Theft of produce)	63(62.4)	33(32.7)	5(5.0)	0(0.0)	2.57	3 rd
Selling of a particular portion of land to several unsuspected buyers	61(60.4)	35(34.7)	4(4.0)	1(1.0)	2.54	6 th
Family institution						
Marital infidelity	68(67.3)	30(29.7)	3(3.0)	0(0.0)	2.64	1 st
Unfaithfulness	55(54.5)	43(52.6)	3(3.0)	0(0.0)	2.51	3 rd
Illegal land grabbing	52(51.5)	36(35.6)	11(10.9)	2(2.0)	2.37	6 th
Gossiping	59(58.4)	36(35.6)	4(4.0)	2(2.0)	2.50	5 th
Child labour	63(62.4)	32(31.7)	5(5.0)	1(1.0)	2.55	2 nd
Prostitution	65(64.4)	27(26.7)	5(5.0)	4(4.0)	2.51	3 rd

VO = Very often (3), O = Often (2), R =Rarely (1), and NA = Not at all (0)

WMS = Weighted Mean Score

Mean = 69.58; S.D = 6.815

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3. Cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers

The findings from cultural integrity items among respondents in Oyo State in terms of moral commitment indicates that keeping of virginity is still an esteemed virtue among rural dwellers with a WMS of 1.17 which ranked 1st, while the other cultural integrity items under moral commitment include detest for bestiality and detest for homosexuality with a WMS of 2.83 which was ranked 1st simultaneously. Under Peaceful coexistence, majority of the respondents reported that community members are still living together without ethnic and political violence / conflict was ranked 1st with a WMS of 1.52. Under Social values, community members show love and maintain obedience as a core values of the community with a WMS of 1.26 and was ranked 1st. Wholeness, community members are in total allegiance to the culture and custom of the community (e.g. unity) with a WMS of 1.23 was ranked 1st. Consistency, community members still practicing the value of firmness in esteeming their moral values E.g. Empathy with a WMS of 1.26 was ranked 1st. Discipline, virtue of self-control still being prioritized in the community with a WMS of 1.32 was ranked 1st. Honesty, it was reported that parents and community leaders still reward and instill the virtue of sincerity and straightforwardness in their children was ranked 1st with a WMS of 1.29. Dutiful, community members are still playing their roles in their households and society as a whole with a WMS of 1.30 was ranked 1st. Social cohesion, community are still practicing the value of togetherness (e.g. Social occasions, Occupations such as-Aroo, Ajo, Esusu) with a WMS of 1.25 was ranked 1st.

Under Mutual respect, the findings revealed that parent are still sharing mutual honour with others in the community irrespective of variation in their social status with a WMS of 1.60 which

was ranked 1st and people esteem and reciprocate paying of homage and reverence to one another in the community with a WMS of 1.31 which was ranked 2nd.

Uprightness, people see social vices as a taboo and strive daily to live just like in the old with a WMS of 1.26 which was ranked 1st, and justice, sincerity and, mercy to less privileges and vulnerable still being upheld in the society with a WMS of 1.23 was ranked 2nd.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers (Oyo State)

Cultural integrity	Frequency (Percentage)					WMS	Rank
	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Not At all	At		
Moral commitment							
i. Keeping of virginity is still an esteemed virtue in their area.	26(25.7)	17(16.8)	6(5.9)	52(51.5)		1.17	1 st
ii. Residents in the community are still frowning at the following moral decadence							
a. Homosexuality	89(88.1)	7(6.9)	5(5.0)	0(0.0)		2.83	1 st
b. Lesbianism	86(85.1)	10(9.9)	5(5.0)	0(0.0)		2.80	4 th
c. Pedophilias	82(81.2)	19(18.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)		2.81	3 rd
d. Bestiality	85(84.2)	15(14.9)	1(1.0)	0(0.0)		2.83	1 st
Peaceful coexistence							
i. Community members are still living together without ethnic and political violence / conflict.	16(15.8)	27(26.7)	52(51.5)	6(5.9)		1.52	1 st
ii. Members of other households still come to visit and even pass the night sometimes without problem.	6(5.9)	34(33.7)	46(45.5)	15(14.9)		1.31	2 nd
Social values							
i. Community members shows love and maintains obedience as a core values of the community.	7(6.9)	33(32.7)	40(39.6)	21(20.8)		1.26	1 st

- ii. Community leaders still teaches and practices responsibility as a good precedence in the community. 6(5.9) 35(34.7) 33(32.7) 27(26.7) 1.20 2nd

Wholeness

- i. Community members are in total allegiance to the culture and custom of their community (e.g. unity). 10(9.9) 30(29.7) 34(33.7) 27(26.7) 1.23 1st
- ii. Community and household heads sees reasons to tenaciously enlighten members on existing cultural practices in the community. 8(7.9) 34(33.7) 30(29.7) 29(28.7) 1.21 2nd

Consistency

- i. Community members are still practicing the value of firmness in esteeming their moral values E.g. Empathy. 12(11.9) 31(30.7) 29(28.7) 29(28.7) 1.26 1st
- ii. Virtue of stability in good deeds is still been taught and rewarded among the communities. 9(8.9) 31(30.7) 35(34.7) 26(25.7) 1.23 2nd

Discipline

- i. Self-control as a virtue is still being prioritized in the community. 12(11.9) 28(27.7) 41(40.6) 20(19.8) 1.32 1st
- ii. Community members sees maintenance of order and keeping of instructions as a virtue that must not be compromised at all cost. 9(8.9) 33(32.7) 35(34.7) 24(23.8) 1.27 2nd

Honesty

- i. Telling of truth is still being practiced and maintained by members in the community. 5(5.0) 34(33.7) 39(38.6) 23(22.8) 1.21 2nd

ii. Parents and community leaders are still rewarding and instilling the virtue of sincerity and straightforwardness in their children.	11(10.9)	22(21.8)	53(52.5)	15(14.9)	1.29	1 st
Dutiful						
i. Community members are playing their roles in their households and society as a whole.	9(8.9)	32(31.7)	40(39.6)	20(19.8)	1.30	1 st
ii. People still cherish obligated diligence and uphold it in the society.	13(12.9)	22(21.8)	46(45.5)	20(19.8)	1.28	2 nd
Social cohesion						
i. Community are still practicing the value of togetherness (e.g. Social occasions, Occupations such as-Aroo, Ajo, Esusu).	13(12.9)	28(27.7)	31(30.7)	29(28.7)	1.25	1 st
ii. They still bond with themselves and uphold the values and virtues of togetherness irrespective of social status and ethnic variation.	16(15.8)	21(20.8)	33(32.7)	31(30.7)	1.22	2 nd
Social identification						
i. People still associate and give solidarity support to one another in the community. (E.g. support for leaders and friends during socials).	9(8.9)	34(33.7)	32(31.7)	26(25.7)	1.26	2 nd
ii. Community still identify themselves in line with clan, family names, compound names and tribal marks.	13(12.9)	30(29.7)	33(32.7)	25(24.8)	1.31	1 st
Mutual respect						
i. Parent are sharing mutual honour with others in the community irrespective of variation in their social status.	25(24.8)	21(20.8)	45(44.6)	10(9.9)	1.60	1 st

ii.	People esteem and reciprocate paying of homage and reverence to one another in their community.	12(11.9)	23(22.8)	50(49.5)	16(15.8)	1.31	2 nd
Decency							
i.	Wearing of clothes that does not reveal sensitive parts of the body is being promoted in their community.	16(15.8)	19(18.8)	44(43.6)	22(21.8)	1.29	2 nd
ii.	People esteem living a blemishless life in their locality. E.g. marital fidelity.	14(13.9)	24(23.8)	42(41.6)	21(20.8)	1.31	1 st
Obedience							
i.	People keep rules and regulation laid down by the community leaders.	11(10.9)	32(31.7)	29(28.7)	29(28.7)	1.25	2 nd
ii.	Children still exhibit swift compliance to parental order like in the old.	15(14.9)	25(24.8)	41(40.6)	20(19.8)	1.35	1 st
Responsibility							
i.	Community leaders are still exercising their authority judiciously to maintain order in the community.	13(12.9)	22(21.8)	46(45.5)	20(19.8)	1.28	2 nd
ii.	Parents are still playing their roles efficiently in the family, so that sanity can be maintained as of old.	11(10.9)	30(29.7)	43(42.6)	17(16.8)	1.35	1 st
Uprightness							
i.	Justice, sincerity and, mercy to less privileges and vulnerable is still being upheld in the society.	11(10.9)	30(29.7)	31(30.7)	29(28.7)	1.23	2 nd
ii.	People sees social vices as a taboo and strive daily to live just like in the old.	14(13.9)	21(20.8)	43(42.6)	23(22.8)	1.26	1 st

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

A = Always (3), S = Sometimes (2), R = Rarely (1), and NA = Not at all (0)

WMS = Weighted Mean Score

Mean = 48.54; S.D = 21.928

Figures in parentheses are percentages

Adopted from page 45, KICG-Forschungspapier Nr. 9 (2015)

4. Categorization of Cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers

The findings in Table 4 shows that, 62.4 percent of the respondents from Oyo State recorded a moderate cultural integrity status level, 24.8 percent recorded a high cultural integrity status while 12.8 percent of the respondents recorded a low cultural integrity status. It was therefore revealed that many of the respondents still maintained moderate cultural integrity status level.

Table 5. Categorization of respondents by the cultural integrity status of the rural dwellers in Oyo State

Categorization	Frequency (Percentage)
High	25(24.8)
Moderate	63(62.4)
Low	13(12.8)
Total	101(100.0)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Oyo State = Mean = 48.54; S.D = 21.928 (26.612-70.468)

Figures in parentheses are percentages

5 HYPOTHESIS

Correlation between various sharp practices in the study area and rural dwellers' cultural integrity status

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between various sharp practices in the study area and rural dwellers' cultural integrity status

Table 5 showed the result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the relationship between various sharp practices and rural dwellers' cultural integrity status. The result of the Pearson's Products Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis in Table 4 indicated that individual sharp practices such as political sharp practices ($r = 0.282^{***}$, 0.004), educational sharp practices ($r = 0.241^{**}$, 0.015) and religion sharp practices ($r = 0.280^{**}$, 0.004) were significant and positively related to rural dwellers' cultural integrity status. This implies that the propensity of safeguarding cultural integrity status increased with a unit increase in the level of sharp practices especially in the political terrain, educational sector and in the religion regime of the rural

communities. This development reveals the grave consequences of diverse sharp practices which generically cumulates into the prevailing weaken moral character of the rural dwellers which implies cultural traditions in Nigeria have therefore been confronted, undermined and transformed with emphasis on riches by most cultural groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between various sharp practices in the study area and rural dwellers’ cultural integrity status was rejected.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the relationship between various sharp practices and rural dwellers’ cultural integrity status in Oyo State

Various Sharp Practices	Correlation Coefficients (r-value)	p-value	Remarks
Politics	0.282***	0.004	S
Education	0.241**	0.015	S
Religion	0.280***	0.004	S
Economic	0.278***	0.004	S
Family	0.121	0.227	NS

S = Significant; NS = Not significant

*****= significant at 1% significance level**

****= significant at 5% significance level**

Source: Data Analysis, 2023

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that ripening of fruits using chemical products was most common sharp practice which falls under the economic institution of the society while keeping of virginity, frowning against homosexuality and bestiality respectively was the topmost cultural integrity item under moral commitment among the rural dwellers. Propensity of safeguarding cultural integrity status increases with a unit decrease in the level of sharp practices especially in the economic, political, family and educational institutions of the rural communities. Therefore, rural dwellers’ especially farmers and traders should desist from unscrupulous acts of ripening fruits with chemicals which is very injurious to consumer’s health. Keeping of virginity also should be encouraged by all and sundry in the society. Leaders and followers in the community and household should imbibe the culture and practice of upholding integrity in their daily living which ranges across the political terrain, educational sector and the religion institutions of the rural communities.

REFERENCES

Bamikole, L. O. (2008). Democracy in a Multicultural Society. *Philosophy and Praxis*, 4, 1-20.

Business Dictionary (2013). www.businessdictionary.com/definition/shap-practice.html

Ladele, A. A. and Fadairo, O. S. (2013). Official corruption and sharp practices as impediments to transforming smallholders to agribusiness: lessons from agricultural development interventions in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Rural Sociology* Vol. 14, No. 1.

Ladele, A.A. and Agboola, O.R. (2015). National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) Beneficiaries and Officers' Perception Conference paper presented at 24th Annual National Congress of Nigerian Rural Sociological Association (NRSA). Changing social values, transparency and sharp practices-impacts on agricultural and rural development. Held between 11-15th of October, 2015, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Oyo State.

Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2018). National Population Commission, Abuja, Nigeria. The DHS Program ICF Rockville, Maryland, USA October 2019. 748 Pp.

OECD (2017). OECD Recommendation on Public Integrity, OECD, Paris, www.oecd.org/gov/ethics/recommendation-public-integrity.htm.